

**TRILLIUM GOVANIUM AND PARIS POLYPHYLLA: A
COMPARATIVE REVIEW OF THEIR PHYTOCHEMISTRY, ENZYME
INHIBITORY PROPERTIES, AND ANTICANCER POTENTIAL**

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ABSTRACT

The Himalayan region is known to be one of the richest reservoirs of diversity of medicinal plants with many species of immense therapeutic and economic importance. Among these, *Trillium govanianum* and *Paris polyphylla* have become two highly important medicinal plants due to their broad ethnomedicinal uses and diverse pharmacological properties. Both species belong to family Melanthiaceae and contain steroidal saponins, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, sterols and other biologically active secondary metabolites (Negi et al., 2014; Rathore et al., 2020). Traditionally, their rhizomes have been employed in the management of wounds, inflammation, infections, reproductive disorders, and various chronic ailments. Scientific investigations have demonstrated antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, enzyme inhibitory, and anticancer activities in extracts and isolated constituents obtained from both species (Rahman et al., 2015; Thapa et al.,

2022). The occurrence of common phytochemical markers such as diosgenin and related steroidal saponins suggests a close chemotaxonomic relationship and provides a scientific basis for comparative evaluation. Furthermore, reports of substitution and interchangeable use of these species in traditional medicinal systems raise important questions regarding their phytochemical equivalence and pharmacological similarities. The enzyme inhibitory properties of these species, including β -glucosidase and β -glucuronidase inhibition, have also

attracted particular interest due to potential relevance in metabolic disorders, inflammation, drug metabolism and cancer-related processes. This review critically summarises the literature available on the taxonomy, ethnobotany, phytochemistry and pharmacological activities of *T. govanianum* and *P. polyphylla* with emphasis on their comparative significance and future prospects in drug discovery research.

KEYWORDS: *Trillium govanianum*, *Paris polyphylla*, Melanthiaceae, steroidal saponins, diosgenin, β -glucosidase, β -glucuronidase, antioxidant activity, anticancer activity.

INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants have been an integral part of health care systems since the beginning of human civilisation. Long before the appearance of synthetic pharmaceuticals, traditional societies used plant-based remedies to prevent and treat a variety of diseases. Medicinal plants are still playing an important role in healthcare especially in developing countries where traditional medicine is an important source of primary healthcare (Manandhar, 2002; Pushpangadan, 1995).

India is a country of great wealth in botany and is recognised as one of the megadiverse countries of the world. The Indian Himalayan Region is one of the major centers of medicinal plant diversity with thousands of species of therapeutic and economic importance (Samant et al., 1998). The unique climatic conditions, varied altitudinal gradients, and ecological heterogeneity of the Himalayas have contributed to the evolution of numerous medicinal plants rich in biologically active secondary metabolites.

Trillium govanianum and *Paris polyphylla* are members of the Himalayan medicinal flora, which have attracted considerable scientific attention due to their ethnomedicinal importance and pharmacological potential. Both the species belong to Melanthiaceae family and are valued mainly for their underground rhizomes rich in steroidal saponins and other biologically active constituents (Ji et al., 2006; Negi et al., 2014). These plants are used extensively in traditional systems of medicine for the treatment of wounds, inflammatory disorders, infections, reproductive disorders and various chronic diseases (Rana et al., 2013; ShahSA et al., 2012).

Steroidal saponins, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, sterols, terpenoids and glycosides have been reported in both the species by phytochemical investigations in modern times (Negi et

al., 2014; Rathore et al., 2020; Rashid et al., 2026). Many of these compounds have been reported to exhibit antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, enzyme inhibitory and anticancer activities, which justify their traditional therapeutic uses (Rahman et al., 2015; Thapa et al., 2022).

While a considerable amount of research has been conducted on the individual pharmacological properties of *T. govaniatum* and *P. polyphylla*, there are rather limited comparative studies. The existence of similar classes of secondary metabolites and overlapping therapeutic applications suggests that these species may have important pharmacological characteristics in common. Knowledge of these similarities and differences is particularly important because the two plants are at times used interchangeably in both traditional medicine and the trade of medicinal plants. Hence, a comprehensive review of their phytochemistry and biological activities is required to assess their therapeutic potential and to direct the future directions of research.

Comparative Significance of *Trillium govaniatum* and *Paris polyphylla*

The scientific rationale for comparing *T. govaniatum* and *P. polyphylla* extends beyond their taxonomic relationship. Both species belong to the family Melanthiaceae and possess several morphological, phytochemical, and ethnomedicinal similarities (Ji et al., 2006; Ding et al., 2021). Their rhizomes constitute the principal medicinal part and represent an important source of steroidal saponins and related bioactive metabolites (Negi et al., 2014; Rathore et al., 2020).

These plants are considered to possess similar therapeutic properties in the traditional medicinal systems of the Himalayan region. The preparations obtained from the rhizomes have been used for healing of wounds, treating inflammation, infections, reproductive disorders and chronic diseases (Rana et al., 2013; Bhattarai et al., 2006). Such similarities have been reported in some areas to result in the interchangeable use and substitution.

Substitution poses significant scientific questions regarding phytochemical equivalence and pharmacological comparability. Where both species are similar in chemical constituents and biological activities, substitution may be justified therapeutically. However, significant differences in the phytochemical composition may affect efficacy, safety and therapeutic outcomes. Hence, scientific basis for such practices must be provided through systematic comparative studies.

Recent phytochemical studies have shown the presence of steroidal saponins, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, sterols, and terpenoids in each of the two species (Negi *et al.*, 2014; Rathore *et al.*, 2020). Comparative phytochemical screening also showed similarities in the classes of secondary metabolites found in their rhizomes (Rashid *et al.*, 2026). However, there is a lack of comparative studies on antioxidant activity, β -glucosidase inhibition, and anticancer potential, which is an important research gap.

Taxonomy and Botanical Description

Trillium govanianum

Trillium govanianum Wall ex D. Don is a perennial herb of the family Melanthiaceae. It is distributed throughout the Himalayan region from India and Pakistan to Nepal, Bhutan and parts of China (Kim *et al.*, 2025; Rathore *et al.*, 2020). In India, large populations are recorded in Jammu and Kashmir, Himachal Pradesh, Uttarakhand and Sikkim (Sharma *et al.*, 2018).

It is common at altitudes of 2,400 to 3,500 m above sea level and is characterised by a stout rhizome, single stem, three leaves in whorls and a terminal flower (Rathore *et al.*, 2020). It is locally known by various names such as Teen Patra and Nag Chhatri (Sharma, 2017).

Paris polyphylla

Paris polyphylla Smith is a rhizomatous perennial herb in the family Melanthiaceae. The species is found in the Himalayan region and East Asia, including India, Nepal, Bhutan, Myanmar and China (Ding *et al.*, 2021; Kunwar *et al.*, 2020). It is commonly found in moist forest ecosystems and grows at elevations between 1500 and 3500 m (Baral & Kurmi, 2006). The plant is characterised by its whorled leaves and solitary terminal flower. Like *T. govanianum* the rhizome is the major medicinal part and is extensively used in traditional medicine (ShahSA *et al.*, 2012).

Ethnomedicinal uses

Medicinal significance of *T. govanianum* and *P. polyphylla* is based on the traditional knowledge systems evolved over centuries. These plants have been used by the indigenous communities of the Himalayan region for the treatment of several diseases indicating their perceived therapeutic value (Mahmood *et al.*, 2012; Kunwar *et al.*, 2020).

The rhizome of *T. govanianum* is traditionally used for the treatment of wounds, dysentery, inflammation, menstrual disorders and reproductive problems (Rana et al., 2013). The plant is also used by folk practitioners as an analgesic and anti-inflammatory remedy which was later supported by pharmacological investigations (Rahman et al., 2016).

Paris polyphylla is an important species in traditional Chinese and Himalayan ethnomedicine. The rhizome has been used to treat wounds, burns, infections, fever, snake bites, inflammatory diseases, and abnormal uterine bleeding (Chinese Pharmacopoeia Commission, 2015; Guo et al., 2008). In China, Rhizoma Paridis is used in several commercially important herbal formulations, such as Yunnan Baiyao and Gong Xue Ning, for wound healing and gynaecological disorders respectively (Guo et al., 2008; Zhao & Shi, 2005).

The extensive traditional use of both species suggests the presence of biologically active compounds that are able to produce therapeutic effects. Modern scientific research in the field of phytochemical and pharmacological studies have increasingly supported the traditional claims, providing further rationale for the continued study of these valuable medicinal plants.

Phytochemical Composition

The high diversity of secondary metabolites is attributed to the therapeutic significance of *Trillium govanianum* and *Paris polyphylla*. Phytochemical investigations of both species during the last two decades have revealed the presence of steroidal saponins, sapogenins, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, sterols, terpenoids, carbohydrates, glycosides, tannins and alkaloids (Negi et al., 2014; Rathore et al., 2020; Thapa et al., 2022).

Secondary metabolites play a crucial role in plant defence and adaptation, but many of these compounds also possess important pharmacological properties in humans. The extraordinary medicinal value of both *T. govanianum* and *P. polyphylla* are mainly linked to their richness in steroidal saponins and related compounds. (Sparg et al., 2004; Negi et al., 2014) Numerous phytochemicals have been identified in both species, but steroidal saponins have been the most extensively investigated group of phytochemicals in both species, given their therapeutic significance, and their potential use as chemotaxonomic markers in the family Melanthiaceae.

Steroidal Saponins

Steroidal saponins are naturally occurring glycosides that consist of a steroidal aglycone attached to one or more sugar residues. These compounds are widely distributed in members of the family Melanthiaceae and have attracted much attention due to their diverse biological activities (Sparg *et al.*, 2004).

From *T. govaniatum*, a number of steroidal saponins have been isolated and characterised such as govanoside A, govanoside B, borassoside E, pennogenin derivatives and diosgenin based glycosides (Ismail *et al.*, 2015; Singh *et al.*, 2020). These compounds are considered to be mainly responsible for the pharmacological properties attributed to the rhizome.

Similarly, *P. polyphylla* is known to be one of the richest sources of steroidal saponins among the Himalayan medicinal plants. Over fifty steroidal saponins have been described from different populations and varieties of the species (Wu *et al.*, 2012a; Thapa *et al.*, 2022). Polyphyllin I, polyphyllin II, polyphyllin VI, polyphyllin VII, dioscin, gracillin and many Paris saponins are important compounds (Chen *et al.*, 1990; Negi *et al.*, 2014).

The presence of structurally related steroidal saponins in both species provides a strong basis for comparative phytochemical studies and may explain the overlap in their traditional medicinal uses.

Diosgenin, a Major Bioactive Constituent

Phytochemical screening of both species revealed the presence of phytochemicals, in particular diosgenin, which is of great importance due to its pharmacological significance and industrial applications. Diosgenin, a steroidal sapogenin is an important precursor in the synthesis of corticosteroids, sex hormones and various steroidal pharmaceuticals (Patel *et al.*, 2012).

Diosgenin is of industrial importance and possesses a broad spectrum of biological activities such as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, antimicrobial and anticancer effects (Liu *et al.*, 2005; Patel *et al.*, 2012). Several studies have shown that diosgenin is capable of modulating multiple signalling pathways involved in carcinogenesis, apoptosis, angiogenesis and metastasis.

The reported ability of diosgenin to suppress fatty acid synthase (FAS) expression is of particular interest, as this enzyme is often overexpressed in various human cancers, including

breast cancer (Patel et al., 2012). Enhanced FAS activity plays a role in tumour growth and survival and is therefore an attractive target for anticancer drug development.

Diosgenin is present in both *T. govaniatum* and *P. polyphylla*, an important chemotaxonomic and pharmacological link between these species and further warrants the comparative assessment of their biological activities.

Phytosterols

Another important class of secondary metabolites reported in both species are phytosterols. They are structurally similar to cholesterol and have been linked to several health-promoting effects, such as anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, immunomodulatory and anticancer activities (Patel et al., 2012).

The phytosterols found in these species are β -sitosterol and stigmasterol. Both compounds have demonstrated the potential for modulation of inflammatory responses, induction of apoptosis in cancer cells, and contribution to maintenance of cellular homeostasis (Piiroinen et al., 2000; Rashid et al., 2026).

Such phytosterols in the presence of steroidal saponins indicate complementary mechanisms that contribute to the overall pharmacological activity of both plants.

Flavonoids and Phenolic Compounds

Both species share important parts of their phytochemical profiles, which include flavonoids and phenolic compounds, known for their antioxidant activity. These compounds serve as free radical scavengers and metal chelators, thus protecting biological systems against oxidative stress (Tungmunnithum et al., 2018).

Studies have confirmed the presence of flavonoids and phenolic constituents in extracts of *T. govaniatum* and *P. polyphylla* (Rahman et al., 2015; Devi et al., 2018). Besides their antioxidant activity, flavonoids have also shown anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antileishmanial and anticancer effects, making them important components in the therapeutic potential of these plants (Tasdemir et al., 2006).

The synergistic biological effects from the combined presence of flavonoids, phenolics and steroidal compounds may result in the increased medicinal value of both the species.

Terpenoids, Glycosides and Other Constituent

Both species contain terpenoids, glycosides, tannins, carbohydrates and other secondary metabolites besides steroidal compounds and flavonoids (Rathore et al., 2020; Thapa et al., 2022).

Terpenoids are known to possess antimicrobial, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties and are known to contribute significantly to the biological activity of medicinal plants (Masyita et al., 2022). Glycosides are a large class of compounds that have effects in many physiological and pharmacological processes.

The presence of these metabolites together with steroidal saponins and flavonoids indicates that the therapeutic properties of *T. govaniatum* and *P. polyphylla* is not due to a single constituent but a synergistic interaction of multiple phytochemical classes.

Comparative Phytochemistry

Comparative phytochemical studies are required to understand the relationship of *T. govaniatum* and *P. polyphylla*. These two species belong to different genera, but they are taxonomically close within the family Melanthiaceae and their phytochemical composition is very similar (Ji et al., 2006; Ding et al., 2021).

The reports available indicate the presence of steroidal saponins, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, sterols, terpenoids, carbohydrates and glycosides in both species (Negi et al., 2014; Rathore et al., 2020). Such similarities may explain their overlapping ethnomedicinal uses and reports of substitution within traditional medicinal systems.

Comparative phytochemical screening of the rhizomes of both plants revealed the presence of common classes of secondary metabolites, further supporting their chemotaxonomic relationship (Rashid et al., 2026). Chromatographic techniques such as High-Performance Thin-Layer Chromatography (HPTLC) have become valuable tools for the rapid characterization, fingerprinting, and quality assessment of medicinal plants, facilitating the identification of bioactive phytochemical markers and comparative evaluation of plant species (Saraf & Saraf, 2020).

The presence of diosgenin and related steroidal compounds in both species is particularly relevant, as these metabolites are often associated with the major biological activities reported for members of the Melanthiaceae.

Quantitative differences in the phytochemical composition are, however, likely to occur despite these similarities. Such variations impact biological activity efficacy and therapeutic outcomes. Hence, further comparative investigations employing sophisticated analytical techniques such as HPTLC, HPLC-MS/MS, LC-QTOF-MS, and metabolomic profiling are needed to elucidate the full chemical relation of these species.

Antioxidant Activity

Oxidative stress is central to the pathogenesis of many chronic diseases including cancer, diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular disorders, neurodegenerative diseases and inflammatory conditions. Reactive oxygen species at excessive levels can oxidatively damage proteins, lipids, and nucleic acids during normal cellular metabolism.(Prakash, 2001; Pisoschi & Negulescu, 2011).

Consequently, natural antioxidants from medicinal plants have attracted a great deal of interest as potential therapeutic agents. Significant antioxidant activity has been demonstrated by both *T. govaniatum* and *P. polyphylla* in a number of experimental systems (Rahman et al., 2015; Devi et al., 2018).

In *T. govaniatum* studies showed that rhizome of possessed antioxidant activity in methanolic extracts and solvent fractions. The activity observed has been mainly attributed to phenolic compounds, flavonoids and steroidal constituents capable of scavenging free radicals and reducing oxidative damage (Rahman et al., 2015).

Comparable antioxidant potential was observed for extracts of *P. polyphylla*. The free radical scavenging activity of the ethanol and the methanol extracts of rhizome has been found to be significant, thereby supporting the traditional use of the plant for various therapeutic applications (Devi et al., 2018; Lepcha et al., 2019).

Antioxidant activity observed in both species is probably due to the synergistic effects of several phytochemical classes including phenolic compounds, flavonoids, steroidal saponins and phytosterols. Such activity may be of great importance in their reported anticancer and anti-inflammatory activities.

Both plants have shown antioxidant properties in individual studies but there is a lack of comparative studies. Direct comparison studies would be useful to understand their relative

antioxidant efficacy and to determine whether similarities in phytochemical composition translate into similar biological activities.

β -Glucuronidase Inhibition Activity

β -Glucuronidase is a lysosomal hydrolase that catalyses the hydrolysis of glucuronic acid conjugates to aglycones and free glucuronic acid. The enzyme is important in the metabolism of endogenous compounds, xenobiotics, hormones and a variety of therapeutic agents. Normal physiological processes depend on β -glucuronidase; however, aberrant or increased activity of this enzyme has been linked to several pathological states such as inflammation, microbial infections, drug-induced toxicity and cancer progression (Rahman et al., 2015).

In recent years, considerable attention has been paid to the discovery of natural β -glucuronidase inhibitors due to their therapeutic potential. The high activity of β -glucuronidase can reactivate toxic metabolites and carcinogens in the tissues, leading to oxidative stress, inflammation and disease development. The inhibition of this enzyme has therefore been promising in the prevention of toxic metabolite accumulation and reducing the risk of different chronic diseases (Rahman et al., 2015).

Medicinal plants are an important source of enzyme inhibitors. Many phytochemicals such as flavonoids, phenolic compounds, alkaloids, terpenoids and steroidal saponins have been reported to have β -glucuronidase inhibitory activity. Such compounds may act by directly interacting with the active site of the enzyme, or by modulating the expression of the enzyme and associated metabolic pathways. The existence of such bioactive constituents has induced the increasing interest in medicinal plants as potential sources of new β -glucuronidase inhibitors.

Among Himalayan medicinal plants, the β -glucuronidase inhibitory activity was significant in rhizome extracts of *T. govianum* reported by Rahman et al. (2015) indicating the presence of bioactive metabolites in the species modulating enzyme activity. The authors attribute this effect to the presence of phytochemicals such as steroidal saponins, phenolic compounds and other secondary metabolites. These findings are indicative of the traditional medicinal importance of the species and suggest its potential for further pharmacological investigation.

However, there are few reports on the β -glucuronidase inhibitory activity of *Paris polyphylla*. The plant's phytochemistry and anti-cancer activity have been extensively studied, but few reports on specific inhibition of β -glucuronidase exist. The significant enzyme inhibitory activity of *P. polyphylla* may also be due to the presence of steroidal saponins, diosgenin derivatives, flavonoids and phenolic compounds similar to those reported in *T. govanianum*. But experimental evidence in support of this hypothesis is scant.

The close taxonomic relationship between *T. govanianum* and *P. polyphylla*, overlapping phytochemical profiles and similar ethnomedicinal applications suggest that comparative studies on β -glucuronidase inhibition may be worthwhile. The present studies may not only increase the understanding of the pharmacological relationship between these species but may also help to identify novel natural inhibitors with potential applications in inflammation management, cancer prevention and drug metabolism research.

β -glucosidase activity inhibition

A major therapeutic approach to treating a variety of disease states is the inhibition of enzymes. Among the different hydrolytic enzymes investigated in recent years, β -glucosidase has been gaining more and more attention due to its involvement in carbohydrate metabolism, microbial physiology, cellular signalling pathways and disease progression.

β -Glucosidases are members of the glycoside hydrolase family and catalyse the hydrolysis of β -glycosidic bonds in a variety of natural substrates. The enzymes are widely distributed in plants, microorganisms and animals, where they participate in essential physiological processes. Alterations in β -glucosidase activity have been linked to various diseases such as lysosomal storage diseases, microbial infections, inflammatory diseases, and metabolic processes related to cancer.

Numerous plant-derived secondary metabolites, including flavonoids, alkaloids, phenolic compounds, terpenoids, and steroidal glycosides, have been reported to exhibit glycosidase inhibitory activity in various medicinal plants. Such compounds can modulate the activity of enzymes by competitive or non-competitive mechanisms that affect the metabolic pathways involved in the development and progression of diseases.

Phytochemical profile of *T. govanianum* and *P. polyphylla* have shown considerable potential for enzyme inhibitory activity. Both species contain a large amount of steroidal

saponins, flavonoids, phenolics and sterols, compounds that have been previously associated with glycosidase inhibition (Negi *et al.*, 2014; Rathore *et al.*, 2020).

The existing literature on the enzyme inhibitory properties of these species is quite scarce, especially in the context of comparative evaluations. Further investigations on β -glucosidase inhibition may provide valuable insights into their therapeutic potential and contribute to the discovery of novel bioactive compounds due to the close taxonomic relationship, phytochemical similarity, and traditional medicinal importance.

Anticancer Activity

Cancer continues to be one of the most difficult health problems globally, and is still responsible for considerable morbidity and mortality worldwide. Despite the significant advances in diagnosis and treatment, conventional chemotherapy still suffers from limitations such as toxicity, multidrug resistance and poor selectivity, stimulating the search for safer and more effective therapeutic alternatives derived from natural products (Newman & Cragg, 2012).

Medicinal plants are the source of many clinically useful anticancer agents. Thus, *T. govanianum* and *P. polyphylla* were selected owing to their abundant steroidal saponins and associated bioactive metabolites.

Anticancer Activity of *Trillium govanianum*

T. govanianum has attracted increasing scientific attention in recent years. The different extracts and isolated compounds from the rhizome showed cytotoxic and antiproliferative activity against various human cancer cell lines (Khan *et al.*, 2016; Lone *et al.*, 2023).

Inhibitory effects were reported against breast cancer (MCF-7), liver cancer (HepG2), lung cancer (A549), bladder cancer (EJ138), cervical cancer (HeLa) and prostate cancer (PC-3) cell lines (Khan *et al.*, 2016). These effects are mainly attributed to steroidal saponins and sapogenins which induce apoptosis, regulate cell cycle progression and disturb cellular proliferation pathways.

In particular, the isolation of new steroidal saponins from *T. govanianum* showed potent cytotoxic activity. These findings support the view that this species is a rich source of bioactive compounds with possible applications for cancer drug development (Lone *et al.*, 2023).

Anticancer Effect of *Paris polyphylla*

Among the pharmacological properties attributed to *P. polyphylla*, anticancer activity is the most extensively investigated. Crude extracts, purified fractions and isolated steroidal saponins have been reported for their effectiveness against a broad spectrum of human cancers (Negi *et al.*, 2014; Thapa *et al.*, 2022).

Polyphyllin I, Polyphyllin II, Polyphyllin D, Polyphyllin VII, dioscin and gracillin were found to be active against breast, lung, liver, colorectal, ovarian, cervical, gastric and prostate cancer cells (Xiao *et al.*, 2009; Wu *et al.*, 2013; Zhang *et al.*, 2018). These compounds act by different molecular mechanisms including apoptosis induction, inhibition of angiogenesis, cell cycle arrest, modulation of oxidative stress and suppression of oncogenic signalling pathways.

The ability of Paris saponins to target multiple cellular pathways simultaneously is considered particularly advantageous, as cancer progression usually involves complex molecular networks rather than a single signalling pathway (Han *et al.*, 2015).

Diosgenin and Steroidal Saponins Mechanisms of Action

Diosgenin and other steroidal saponins are widely accepted as the major bioactive compounds responsible for a plethora of reported pharmacological activities in *T. govanianum* and *P. polyphylla* (Negi *et al.*, 2014; Rathore *et al.*, 2020).

Diosgenin has been shown to modulate multiple cellular processes involved in cancer development and progression. Liu *et al.* (2005) reported that the compound can induce apoptosis, inhibit cellular proliferation, inhibit angiogenesis, modulate inflammatory responses, and affect several signalling pathways involved in tumour growth.

One very important mechanism is inhibition of the expression of fatty acid synthase (FAS). FAS is often overexpressed in various human malignancies including breast cancer and it plays a role in cellular proliferation, invasion and survival (Patel *et al.*, 2012). Therefore, the inhibition of FAS has emerged as a promising therapeutic strategy in oncology.

Correspondingly, steroidal saponins obtained from either species have been shown to modulate apoptosis-related proteins, activate caspase pathways, alter mitochondrial membrane permeability, and inhibit signalling pathways such as PI3K/Akt, NF- κ B and MAPK (Xiao *et al.*, 2009; Feng *et al.*, 2019).

This diversity of mechanisms suggests that steroidal saponins may offer advantages over single-target therapeutics and highlights their potential as lead molecules in the future discovery of anticancer drugs.

Research Gaps

Despite the extensive investigations on the phytochemistry and pharmacological activities of *T. govanianum* and *P. polyphylla*, there are still many critical gaps in the existing literature.

Most studies have focused on the individual assessment of each species, whereas direct comparative studies are still scarce. Both plants belong to the family Melanthiaceae and have similar classes of secondary metabolites but the extent of their phytochemical similarity is yet to be explored fully (Negi *et al.*, 2014; Rathore *et al.*, 2020).

Another important gap relates to the traditional substitution and interchangeable use of these species in some medicinal systems. Substitution has been reported but not enough scientific evidence exists to support such practices. Therefore, comparative studies on phytochemical composition, antioxidant activity, enzyme inhibition and anticancer efficacy are needed.

Moreover, due to the growing therapeutic importance of glycosidase inhibitors, very little data are available on the inhibitory activity of β -glucosidase. Comparative studies on this aspect may significantly contribute to the knowledge of the medicinal value of these species. Although β -glucuronidase inhibitory activity has been reported in *Trillium govanianum*, comparable investigations involving *Paris polyphylla* are largely lacking, and no comprehensive comparative evaluation of these two closely related medicinal species has been reported to date (Rahman *et al.*, 2015).

Future investigations should focus on comprehensive comparative evaluation of phytochemical composition, antioxidant activity, β -glucosidase inhibition, β -glucuronidase inhibition, and anticancer mechanisms. Such studies will help clarify the pharmacological similarities and differences between *Trillium govanianum* and *Paris polyphylla* and provide scientific evidence regarding their traditional medicinal use and substitution.

Finally, despite the promising biological activities observed in many *in vitro* studies, clinical evidence remains scarce. More studies in animal models, pharmacokinetics, toxicity studies and clinical trials are needed to confirm the therapeutic efficacy and safety.

Outlook for the future

Future studies should be directed towards detailed comparative studies involving phytochemical profiling, metabolomics, molecular docking, network pharmacology and advanced bioassays. Such studies would permit better understanding of the similarities and differences between *T. govanianum* and *P. polyphylla* (Saraf & Saraf, 2020).

The identification of bioactive markers like diosgenin, β -sitosterol, stigmasterol, polyphyllins, and related steroidal saponins might be useful in the development of standardised quality-control protocols and may improve the consistency of medicinal plant products.

Moreover, systematic evaluation of β -glucosidase and β -glucuronidase inhibitory activity, antioxidant capacity and mechanisms of anticancer activity may potentially open new avenues for the discovery of novel therapeutic agents and scientific validation of traditional medicinal practices.

CONCLUSION

Trillium govanianum and *Paris polyphylla* are two important medicinal plants of the family Melanthiaceae with considerable ethnopharmacological importance and diverse biological activities. Both species are abundant sources for steroidal saponins, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, sterols and other secondary metabolites which contribute to their therapeutic potential.

A comparative investigation is warranted by the presence of common bioactive constituents, particularly diosgenin and related steroidal compounds. Existence of steroidal saponins as the main contributor to their pharmacological activities has been highlighted in existing studies that proved their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, enzyme inhibitory and anticancer activities.

Despite the growing scientific interest, comparative studies are still limited, particularly with regard to phytochemical profiling, β -glucuronidase inhibition, and anticancer mechanisms. The reported substitution of one species for the other in traditional medicinal systems further emphasises the need for systematic comparative evaluation. Future research combining phytochemistry, molecular pharmacology and clinical validation will improve our understanding of the species and enable their use in evidence-based drug discovery and development.

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